

Examination of Local Connections in terms of Education Quality in School Management

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Abstract

As the school's parent, he is the person responsible for bringing the school's activities to life. According to all the people involved in my research, it is perfectly acceptable to seek or provide guidance from the principal or head teacher . A few participants even suggested that principals should be responsible for tasks that were difficult for their colleagues. An informer female teacher recognizes the importance of a head teacher's position and expresses her belief that when a head teacher supports ethical standards, other instructors are more likely to avoid engaging in unethical behavior. In this way, they can perform their duties effectively. In fact, if we want people to think positively about a school, the principal should not leave any negative impressions and instead should encourage other lecturers to do a better job. However, the day-to-day operations of the head teacher position are not standardized from one individual to the next. The characteristics of people often have an impact on their understanding of the ethical world. As a result, it is very necessary to investigate the ethical behaviors of school principals by considering the unique characteristics of each situation. Some school principals are tired of the constant struggle to maintain ethics in their institutions. For example, many believe that politics poses a significant barrier to the school principal's effective fulfillment of his obligations. Because school principals are often active in politics, which helps them do their jobs at their own convenience, they tend to be more accountable to local politics than to school. Because politics supports them while doing their jobs according to their individual comfort. According to one head teacher , even if a person meets all promotion standards, it is difficult to get promoted without the support of influential political officials. My schoolwork should stay in the background when visiting influential people who can help us move forward. The previous comment made by the school principal is not correct when referring to principals of other schools. They believe that individual dedication and success are primary factors in progress. This shows that the personal thoughts and feelings of principals and other school leaders also have an impact on the efficient functioning of schools.

Keywords: Educational Psychology, Educational Administration , Headteacher Concept, Educator's Responsibilities, Educational Administrators

Introduction

Starrat (2005), the involvement of professional teachers and other stakeholders is believed to be crucial in maintaining appropriate ethics on behalf of principals in schools. On the other hand, many who participated in my research believe that the participation of the teachers' union in the ethical actions of school administrators and principals should be improved. The union has its own district line authority. He supports every head teacher and other lecturers in the school, even if they are not able to fulfill their responsibilities in the most effective way. Although government officials plan to discipline principals in accordance with the policy document, they are legally prohibited from doing so. When such a scenario arises, members of the professional association rush to help.

On the other hand, the school principal cannot do anything about the issue. Despite having evidence of the teachers at the school behaving inappropriately, the principal is unable to address the issue with them. This came about because of her currently working under the authority of an unidentified teachers' union.

The ideas put forward by the head teacher are not welcomed by the other lecturers. There are many different reasons why school principals are not good at organizing events for their schools. In this context, politics is his primary interest. On the other hand, some educators are of the opinion that professional teacher unions are responsible for unethical business activities. From an educator's perspective, teachers' unions should train their members in ethical behavior. On the other hand, the function of the union is a controversial issue.

There are also instances where educators are unaware of the choices made by these professional bodies. All of the people participating in the research stated that the professional association was established to protect the rights and welfare of the participants' own groups; therefore, it is impossible to reject the union as unnecessary . However, unethical behaviors of school principals to participate in union activities and avoid their responsibilities at school cannot be considered beneficial for schools. One of the students expressed the view that the operation of the union should not interfere with the activities of teachers and students. He says that educators should act in

accordance with the values determined by their organizations. However, they must continue to fulfill their obligations, considering their needs. He continues by emphasizing that teachers should not make complaints about their students to government officials. Our teachers are people we see as role models and are also responsible for spreading knowledge in our community. This shows that school stakeholders are not satisfied with the functions the teachers union plays in the school. In various contexts, it is not helpful for principals and other education leaders to do this. However, to successfully implement the curriculum in their school, some department heads of the school receive assistant help. For example, the officials of a professional association in a school contribute to maintaining friendly relations with teachers. The head teacher adjusts his management's plans based on the feedback provided by the trainers. Therefore, as noted in the previous statement, the availability of union assistance is very context dependent and varies from one region to another. Because the union is a political organization.

However, these standards do not work as intended, as there is no reliable monitoring mechanism yet. If there is no reliable monitoring mechanism in place, it is possible that the application will not take full effect. One of the people involved in this study took a similar view, as he mentioned that teachers are often accused of being unethical because our policy implementation and monitoring system is inefficient. The state has established the code of conduct, but there is no sector to examine whether it is applied correctly. The state has drawn up the code of conduct. After the implementation phase, a monitoring system should come.

Methodology

Some of the respondents believed it is the duty of the state to implement policies. It is necessary to get the support of different political parties, who often emphasize how important it is for the government to fulfill its duties. It is difficult for a ruling party to monitor whether policies are being implemented effectively in the local environmental context without the cooperation of other political parties. This represents a challenge for the ruling party. On the other hand, the party that currently governs the state cannot successfully implement the policies that have been created. In many cases, they place political agents in various roles, and in many of these circumstances they do so even though they cannot effectively carry out the policies of the state. What these political operators consider when doing their job is the interests of their respective parties. This shows very clearly that policy guidelines are not helpful in maintaining ethics in schools. One survey

participant observed about accountability: "If someone is hired because of the leader's political influence, that person is more accountable to the leader than the job itself." When formulating a policy guideline for ethics, government should consider this issue before proceeding further.

Inconsistency Between Policies and Practices

At this point, the question arose as to why policies did not address the need for ethics on behalf of the principal. During the interviews and focus groups, the vast majority of those involved in the education system expressed dissatisfaction with the ineffectiveness of the policy-making process. There are several situations where stakeholders are significantly less likely to develop an ethical school policy, and each of these situations is unique.

The population is responsible for formulating the nation's educational policy. This indicates that the top-down method for policy making for school ethics does not work very effectively. At the local level, the policies formulated at the central level have been modified to reflect the changes.

When the teacher said this, he meant that he and some other teachers were engaged in a profession that suited them. This shows that government policy and standards are followed differently in schools and government norms and expectations are often not met at the local level. For local people at school level to properly exercise their authority, they need to be given the tools to do so. One head teacher, who has been in the profession for a considerable time, concluded that the ineffectiveness, not the current environment, of schools was responsible for government intervention. He argued that in order to provide reasonable benefits to teachers, the government should transfer the authority to collect fees from students who can pay, and he said this about the government. I've heard him talk about the contextual challenges that need to be addressed in his policy statement, and we've also seen him talk about fee collection. In this context, some respondents claimed that the government's involvement also caused uncertainty in the public opinion due to the lack of complete transparency of policies. People have their own unique way of interpreting policies. According to the current education system in our country, all students have the right to receive free education up to and including secondary education level. This is expressed by a head teacher. This indicates that a student can study at a school without paying any tuition fees. However, there are some parents who believe that their child's educational experience should be completely free to them. Regarding the ethical practices of principals, there are some debates and misunderstandings about the implementation of school policies. Respondents saw that a

discussion was necessary in formulating ethical principles that principals should follow at the local level. At the school level, certain activities are available, such as holding school meetings and recording the minutes of such sessions. On the other hand, the choice to hold a meeting is usually one that is negotiated for a few days or weeks and then abandoned. To combat the problem of unethical behavior, one school principal expressed his view as follows: "As a school principal, we consider it vital to establish a code of conduct in every school."

Theoretical Foundations for Ethical Policies and Practices

Bhattarai (2010), scholars often disagree on how to explain ethical principles. Objectivism was the dominant school of thought when ethics was first discussed, but subjectivism soon replaced it as the dominant school of thought. In the following years, some philosophers came to the conclusion that subjectivism and objectivity should be combined. As a result, the philosophical school known as "antisubjectivism" was founded. It is possible to trace the origins of traditional, relational, communitarian and communicative theories to intersubjectivity, which forms the conceptual basis of many of these approaches. In contractual philosophy, as Bowden (2005) points out, a significant amount of weight is said to be given to justice and rights. Respect for the freedom and equal moral worth of every human being can be expressed in several different ways (Jennings, 2003). One of these ways is to enumerate the basic political, social and human rights shared by all individuals. This is an alternative way of communicating the idea that each individual should be considered on the same level as the others. Moral difficulties with rights and justice can manifest in a society in several different ways;

"The nature and manifestation of these challenges can vary from place to place and change throughout human history."

At the local level, it can be difficult to make generalizations derived from the text at the state level. Conventionalism is a school of thought that holds the belief that moral norms are the product of society's consensus on what is right and wrong. The philosopher Thomas Hobbes was a supporter of this viewpoint. According to this hypothesis (Hinman, 1994), those who act ethically on a daily basis are those who believe that moral principles exist in the form of socially accepted concepts. The hypothesis is based on the idea that ethical behavior occurs with some regularity in the activities that people engage in on a daily basis.

One of the most important factors to consider when trying to understand what it means to live a moral life is relationships. According to Bhattarai (2010), Gilligan's view on ethics was heavily influenced by the feminist approach. This approach claims that moral life is essentially about caring for other people and maintaining relationships. This concept establishes a link between morality and concerns about the racial and ethnic diversity of our society, as well as gender issues. This perspective changes not only from one field to another, but also over time and history. And these are features associated with the local context; It is difficult to avoid the variation that develops from the local context to seek a broader generalized understanding of what is going on. This theory can be associated with research to monitor and evaluate the extent to which schools' main stakeholders take their rights and freedoms into account in the process of creating locally meaningful morale for the school principal. Robinson and Garratt (2004) state that what is discussed when talking about the collectivist part of ethical philosophy is the contextual component of society. A school's student population and staff will often be diverse in terms of gender and ethnicity, in addition to differences in cultural background and economic status. Therefore, it is extremely important for the school's key stakeholders to understand what the school leader's code of ethics is and what type of ethics will be most appropriate for the school's students and teachers (Bhattarai , 2012).

Another important school of thought in ethics is the German philosopher Jurgen . It is the communicative ethics theory developed by Habermas . The legitimacy of moral norms is said to be established through a kind of social contract that takes the form of dialogue if one subscribes to this school of thought. According to communication theory, it is necessary to maintain strong bonds with parents, students and other educators through the use of discourse in order to develop the moral principles of school principals in an educational setting. This is an important component to achieve this goal. In order to keep such relations alive, it is very important that many stakeholders establish dialogues among themselves that create an atmosphere of mutual respect.

Bhattarai (2010), discussion can involve a wide variety of contextual issues and can be used in the process of developing ethical standards in an organizational context. This is something that can be advantageous for the process. The preceding discussion makes it clear that ethical policy is embedded in the local context. As a result, a document issued by the highest authority or the state does not acceptably address the unique ethical issues of the local community. Therefore, it creates

a moral dilemma for many stakeholders in the organization, which causes them to feel confused and contradictory. However, there should be further discussion about the idea of involving subject matter experts in the investigation of ethical principles in specific educational settings.

Interaction differs from region to region and any document submitted between school stakeholders has the potential to dominate interactions ; The document can open the way to organize the discussion. Any document provided between school stakeholders is also likely to dominate interactions. Additionally, any document displayed among school stakeholders has the potential to drive debate.

Whatever the various moral behaviors that may be seen in a school, they all depend to some extent on the traditions maintained in the institution. It is reasonable to expect the principal, who is also a member of society, to comply with established standards of ethical behavior in educational institutions. These principles, attained by consensus, ultimately lay the groundwork for ethical behavior. In addition, it is often recognized that the school principal plays a crucial role in the moral management of educational institution-related issues. If the principal of an institution is or tries to be ethical, other teachers working in that institution will be less likely to engage in unethical activities. This is a once-in-a-lifetime situation, and as a result, the repercussions are different for each individual who experiences it. On the other hand, it is the responsibility of professional teacher associations to monitor and ensure compliance with ethical standards and procedures in schools. It is also possible that the purpose of the association has somehow changed from one site to another. Policy guidelines shed light on numerous different ethical issues prevalent in the organization as a whole. It can act as a guide in the development of ethical rules and processes in educational institutions.

Since teacher behavior norms are expected to be in line with the policies, the guidelines developed by the state are thought to be effective in schools. A government-developed policy statement, on the other hand, can be read in a variety of ways, depending on your location. Additionally, contextual questions are always the way to build school principals to make them ethical within the context of the society in which they operate. Convention, state law, contextual understandings, individual thinking, and teachers' union all have their share in defining the ethical practices currently used by principals. Each of these factors contributes in its own unique way. Contextual issues, individual thinking and traditional ideas are hardly taken into account when it comes to the

development and implementation of national laws for head teacher ethics in schools. This is the case in terms of the ethical principles applied by the school principals in the place where this study was conducted. They focus on the currently in force policies established by the country's education law, as corrective measures to overcome the existing ethical problem in the educational setting . This was done to overcome the problem posed by the nation's education law. The individual needs to make an honest and first effort to maintain ethics within the school, and the first step in this effort is to focus on examining the many aspects of the school in addition to the socio -economic and cultural environment that created it .

[This Is The First Step Of This Effort](#)

It goes without saying that addressing these aspects in the local context will be helpful in maintaining ethical standards in educational contexts; I'll point out anyway. As a result, it is essential to ensure that local stakeholders of schools are involved in the formulation of basic ethical policies for schools. There is currently no such provision. If the policy statement to the government did not include such protections, it would be impossible to develop a set of ethical principles that would be useful to school administrators . On the other hand, this situation can lead to the emergence of many destructive behaviors in the environments where educational activities are carried out. As a result, educational theorists need to move away from the prevailing thinking of identifying a single model that can protect ethics in all socioeconomic settings. Instead, they must adopt a paradigm to find a contextual model that is appropriate for each school .

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Moral difficulties with rights and justice can manifest in a society in several different ways; The nature and manifestation of these challenges may vary from place to place and have changed throughout human history. At the local level, it can be difficult to make generalizations derived from the text at the state level. Conventionalism is a school of thought that holds the belief that moral norms are the product of society's consensus on what is right and wrong. The philosopher Thomas Hobbes was a supporter of this viewpoint. According to this hypothesis (Hinman , 1994), those who act ethically on a daily basis are those who believe that moral principles exist in the form of socially accepted concepts. The hypothesis is based on the idea that ethical behavior occurs with some regularity in the activities that people engage in on a daily basis. From this point of view, the following question comes to mind: "Can ethical standards emerging from the central authority work in every environment on the axis of 'social consensus'?" from one location to another and over time? One of the most important factors to consider when trying to understand what it means to live a moral life is relationships. According to Bhattarai (2010), Gilligan's view on ethics was heavily influenced by the feminist approach. This approach claims that moral life is essentially about caring for other people and maintaining relationships. This concept establishes a link between morality and concerns about the racial and ethnic diversity of our society, as well as gender issues. This perspective changes not only from one field to another, but also over time and history. For example, the idea of gender inequalities and interactions in Nepalese society has changed and changed over many years as a direct result of events that have occurred in the nation's history. And these are features associated with the local context; It is difficult to avoid the variation that develops from the local context to seek a broader generalized understanding of what is going on.

from the literature

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component of society. A school's student population and staff will often be diverse in terms of gender and ethnicity, in addition to differences in cultural background and economic status. Therefore, it is extremely important for the school's key stakeholders to understand what the school leader's code of ethics is and what type of ethics will be most appropriate for the school's students and teachers (Bhattarai , 2012). Another important school of thought in ethics is the German philosopher Jurgen . It is the communicative ethics theory developed by Habermas . The legitimacy of moral norms is said to be established through a kind of social contract that takes the form of dialogue if one subscribes to this school of thought. According to communication theory, it is necessary to maintain strong bonds with parents, students and other educators through the use of discourse in order to develop the moral principles of school principals in an educational setting. This is an important component to achieve this goal. In order to keep such relations alive, it is very important that many stakeholders establish dialogues among themselves that create an atmosphere of mutual respect. According to Bhattarai (2010), discussion can involve a wide variety of contextual issues and can be used in the process of developing ethical standards in an organizational context. This is something that can be advantageous for the process. The preceding discussion makes it clear that ethical policy is embedded in the local context. As a result, a document issued by the highest authority or the state does not acceptably address the unique ethical issues of the local community. Therefore, it creates a moral dilemma for many stakeholders in the organization, which causes them to feel confused and contradictory. However, there should be further discussion about the idea of involving subject matter experts in the investigation of ethical principles in specific educational settings. Interaction differs from region to region and any document submitted between school stakeholders has the potential to dominate interactions ; The document can open the way to organize the discussion. Any document provided between school stakeholders is also likely to dominate interactions. Additionally, any document displayed among school stakeholders has the potential to drive debate.

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of identifying a single model that can protect ethics in all socioeconomic settings. Instead, they must adopt a paradigm to find a contextual model that is appropriate for each school . This model should take into account the sociocultural of the surrounding region and the interactions that take place on a daily basis.

Argument

There are some gray areas in the distribution of tasks, and central-level agencies are responsible for managing some of the issues that need to be delegated. One of them is the field of non-formal education. Buildings and other resources, such as computers and textbooks, are provided to provincial schools by the Ministry of Education as part of various development programs. Having a significant number of subject administrators at the center means that they frequently participate in activities conducted by provincial schools at the practice level. These programs should include an appropriate selection of fieldwork that can bring about behavioral changes in trainees .

Regional Level Planning

In order to collect data and information on planning at the zoning level, interviews were conducted both individually and in groups. Officials responsible for planning at the regional level were knowledgeable about planning and had a positive attitude towards planning. In addition, they are motivated to improve their Regions through strategic planning . The planning team needs more training in methodologies and international trends related to training planning. While involving many stakeholders in the planning process is critical to successful implementation, some planning officers fail to grasp its importance. Monitoring systems intended to serve as a practical tool in the regions are not of the quality expected of them. Therefore, schools are not adequately supervised and students are not given the proper guidance they need. One of the reasons for this is the lack of sufficient number of personnel in the regional directorates. ii. Insufficient funding from the province is one of the problems that the regions are currently dealing with. Even if the allocations are distributed, there is no cash flow to the regions. As a result, districts are unable to provide schools with the necessary funding to create projects or participate in events. There are some regions that have created annual implementation plans in line with the education sector development framework and program issues, but not five-year plans . On the other hand, some problems in certain regions are not sufficiently fixed. In some of the regions visited, there was a shortage of personnel and equipment for the planning units .

The work of educating students takes place in the classroom through interaction between the students and the teacher, made possible by a conducive environment in the school. Although there are complex structures for the management and supervision of schools in central and rural areas, the main student training takes place in private teaching institutions. Schools are biological institutions that should have their own unique identity as they mature and evolve on their own. They are people-centered and the importance of human interactions to their success cannot be overstated. Due to the myriad ways in which educational institutions differ from one another, it is impossible to enforce uniform bureaucratic arrangements . As a result, educational institutions need to be given a certain amount of autonomy, even though they are governed by broad norms established by higher authorities. Consequently, decentralization must be realized down to the school level. It goes without saying that increased monitoring and accountability are crucial when it comes to delegation. In certain places, the center has more powers, but in other places the school is given more room to make its own decisions. As this has been going on for over a decade, it is time for us to assess the situation and make further improvements in the way the idea is implemented. After all, the community that the school serves has a responsibility to be responsible for, and the community has the right to participate in school management.

Complaints were received about poor governance of schools and accusations of unscrupulous practice . The answer to these questions is to ensure that school operations are conducted in an open and transparent manner with the participation of representatives from the local community. In the next five to ten years, a strategy should be developed to significantly strengthen educational institutions. Recruitment of qualified teachers in the appropriate staff by the school as part of the empowerment process based on the regulations set by the MoNE. The construction of new structures must be done on a need-only basis, and the government must provide both funding and labor.

also aims to identify the conditions under which they take the initiative, rather than over-validating the results of taking the initiative .

As a result, it has been determined that the following sub-goals are important for the study:

1. *Do school administrators encounter problems that cannot be explained by the laws and rules that govern them?*

2. *What kind of solutions do school administrators resort to when legal texts, bylaws and rules do not describe the situation or do not provide sufficient guidance?*
3. *Do school administrators use their own initiative rather than more rigorously approving and adhering to rules and regulations ?*
4. *What are the principles, values, regulations and ethical framework followed by school administrators in the enterprise process?*
5. *What kind of results can we expect from school administrators taking the initiative in certain situations?*

The case study, also known as a single case study, is one of the qualitative research methodologies . This research, which aims to determine the perspectives of school administrators on the conditions and consequences of taking initiative in decision making, is structured as a case study (single case study). A type of qualitative research is called a case study, and its main components are the description and analysis of a particular system, which is somewhat circumscribed. In a case study, a contemporary phenomenon is often studied by placing it in the context of real-world events. A constrained system will be the focus of review in this particular study. One definition of a closed system is one in which the subject of investigation is restricted to a single person, program, organization, institution, community, or unique policy. In a case study, the researcher focuses on the phenomenon in question to characterize the interaction of the relevant components associated with the phenomenon in question. The approach is the model in which the researcher examines the limited scenario in detail using the data and then summarizes the themes related to this situation and reports it. The problem addressed in the present review is the formation of ideas brought about by the law on the appointment of school heads. In other words, school administrators' views on the use of initiative conditions will serve as the unit of analysis for this case study.

The methodology , known as an interview , is a procedure in which both the interviewer and the interviewee take part by focusing on questions related to the topic of the study. The term "interview" refers to a particular type of encounter [32]. Interviewing is a method that can be used to effectively describe behaviors, emotions and expressions that cannot be witnessed directly. For this reason, the interview technique was used as a data collection tool in the research conducted to examine the changes in the ideas and opinions of school administrators regarding the conditions, reasons and results of taking initiative in administrative procedures. In order to collect personal

information, questions in semi-structured form were designed using a flexible language. The questions in the interview form were developed to focus on the topics expected to be discussed.

The work consists of five stages:

- (i) *Preparation of Interview Questions,*
- (ii) *Data Collection,*
- (iii) *Analysis of Data,*
- (iv) *Evaluation of Validity and Reliability and*
- (v) *Interpretation of Data.*

Conclusion

At this stage of the research, the interview form to be used in data collection was prepared. Consensus was achieved among the experts, and then the categories developed by the authors were compared. This allowed the identification of a number of areas of agreement and disagreement. The reliability of the study was determined using the method developed by Miles and Huberman [35], which states that reliability is obtained by dividing the number of agreements by the total number of agreements and disputes. Similarly, some possible answers include exploring other programs, working out, or contacting an experienced administrator. The idea of initiative is useful for managers because it enables them to better understand the organizational structure and the dynamics in the management process. Additionally, it helps managers understand the fundamentals of democratic decision-making processes. However, the findings of the study reveal that school administrators are left to their own devices in the process of taking initiative activities and that their initiative-taking skills do not have an effect on the whole school. As a result, taking the initiative failed to encourage creative thinking and strategic planning; rather, he seemed to favor the rationalization of bureaucratic procedures and pragmatism. The findings of the research firstly showed that the school administrators participating in the research did not take initiative to achieve the organizational goals defined in the literature, did not make active decisions to solve organizational problems, and did not show their will to make decisions. Instead, they used their initiative in conditions that presented only minimal danger, allowed them to avoid being watched, and did not require much insight or originality on their part. These initiative behaviors revealed a

tendency to be in the present and to think pragmatically. School administrators reported experiencing a wide variety of unpleasant emotions, including uncertainty, conflict, anxiety, inadequacy, fear of being victimized, and anxiety of being investigated.

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